

Entropy as a Description of the Interactions in a System?

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Statistical mechanics seems to be a theory based on predicting probabilities for systems which have some information removed. For example, in classical mechanics each particle has a known p, v, x, t and energy, but if one removes the variable t , then one reduces the information which leads to a statistical treatment, i.e. the analysis of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (with or without a potential). In other words, if t is removed, one does not know the amount of time a particle spends in a state with energy e , or momentum p and so this must be predicted probabilistically. Nevertheless, the problem is still highly deterministic because precise values of x, p, v and energy are still known for a particle. A second important consideration is that there exist two types of interactions occurring: statistical two particle interactions and a deterministic interaction with a potential $V(x)$. Even with a piece of information removed, namely t , it seems that the two particle interaction is key to the problem, yet one maximizes entropy subject to a constraint. The constraint: $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave}$ is generic and so it seems that the entropy expression, which is considered as either $-k \ln(\text{number of states})$ or $-k \sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$, is really a description of the interaction. In particular, one may derive $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ strictly from probabilistic considerations of an interaction with no notion of entropy used. As a result, it may be that one does not really need to consider an entropy expression in all statistical problems.

In particular, in quantum mechanics, a particle with momentum p is described by a kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$ which breaks down the idea of a precise x and p together. $\exp(ipx)$ is already based on maximum entropy for points within ruler gradations of size \hbar/p . Classically, the Newtonian idea of force and impulse hits still holds in a system with a potential $V(x)$. An $\exp(ipx)$ should still undergo an impulse hit due to a potential, but it is not clear at which x point this occurs. Given that $V(x)$, which represents precise potential energy information at x , and delivers an impulse hit, by the same reasoning used for $\exp(ipx)$, an impulse hit from $V(x)$ must be associated with a probability $\exp(ikx)$. One has entangled probabilities, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ entangled with $\exp(ikx)$, and one cannot write an entropy expression simply in terms of particle properties as is done in classical statistical mechanics. In particular, if one uses $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$, there is no way to bias the outcome and still have constant energy at each x point.

As a result, one wishes to describe the interaction as well as any constraints. The interaction of $\exp(ipx)$ with $V_k \exp(ikx)$ involves entangled entropy and already contains the energy constraint. It seems that one does not have an independent entropy expression which only describes particle attributes which are maximized subject to an energy constraint. Rather, a description of the interaction in terms of probabilities automatically involves $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ s, $V_k \exp(ikx)$ s and includes the energy constraint in one expression, namely the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The fact that there is one solution for $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for a single E_n shows that there are no further degrees of freedom which may be adjusted.

In the case of a photon being absorbed by a bound state, one loses all information about the interaction of the photon with the system and only focuses on its energy and the energy of bound states. Energy is really the only variable in the system and one has a deterministic

problem, like in classical mechanics. The quantum states are like the particles and one may write an entropy in terms of these and maximize it subject to an average energy constraint. Thus, the interaction is decoupled from the states. In other words, there is no consideration of any entropy or specific interaction associated with the photon in the calculation.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Entropy

Classical mechanics follows a particle in time through $x(t)$ and shows all of its interactions in time. If time is removed, one cannot see the interactions in time and one has a classical statistical mechanics problem. If one cannot see the interactions and if average probabilities $f(e_i)$ do not change in time, one has equilibrium. In classical statistical mechanics, it is suggested that this equilibrium is linked to maximizing a function which describes the possible degrees of freedom of the particles subject to a constraint, e.g. an energy constraint:

$$\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is generic and really says almost nothing about the interaction, namely two body scattering. Entropy, on the other hand, is portrayed as a special function describing the possible degrees of freedom of the particle, i.e.

$$S = -k \ln(\text{number of states}) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{Boltzmann}$$

$$S = -k \sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((2b)) \quad \text{Gibbs and Shannon}$$

We argue, as we have in previous notes, that it is the interaction which is key. In other words, the expression of entropy is actually a description of the kind of interaction which exists and is maximized to remove any bias from this interaction. In particular, for two body elastic scattering:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

((3b)) already removes all sense of bias so no maximization is needed.

Taking \ln of ((3b)) and equating it to a constant, $-1/T$, multiplied by ((3a)) yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution without any consideration of entropy, as we have noted before. Thus, maximizing an entropy expression is equivalent to this particular type of interaction. One may fix T by using the average energy constraint: $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E_{ave}$.

The question then becomes: Does one always have an entropy expression to maximize subject to constraints for any interaction? We suggest that one does not in the case of a quantum bound state and so maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is not a universal procedure.

Quantum Bound State

It seems that the notion of entropy is present in the description of a free particle probability, $\exp(ipx)$. This expression creates ruler gradations of length \hbar/p with equal weights, or maximum entropy for points within each \hbar/p region. In fact, one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ by maximizing a Shannon's entropy expression subject to a constraint $-\int p \times f(px)$.

How does one deal with a bound state with a $V(x)$. $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that a free particle with p cannot be at a given x with certainty and so the usual classical approach of following a particle at x cannot be used. $V(x)$ must then describe average energy at x because it cannot describe exact energy corresponding to an exact p at x . Newtonian mechanics suggests that $V(x)$ is linked with force or impulse hits, but then these too must have the form $V_k \exp(ikx)$. As a result, V_k represents energy, while $\exp(ikx)$ is a probability linked to an impulse hit and maximum entropy within an \hbar/k region.

We have argued above that one must statistically describe the interaction, not write an entropy expression. It seems that to do this, one may write:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \text{ average } ((4))$$

One may note that entropy does appear anywhere, but neither does an interaction between $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ at first glance.

Writing: $KE_{ave}(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((5)) one may write:

$$-1/2m \ d^2W/dx^2 + V(x)W(x) = E_n W(x) ((5))$$

In such a case: $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ shows interactions with $W(x)$. In other words, entropy of $\exp(ipx)$ s is entangled with entropy of $V_k \exp(ikx)$ s with the average energy constraint built-in. We suggest that describing an interaction a priori with the probabilities present is the general way of tackling a problem. It is possible that such an approach may be equivalent to maximizing a math function called entropy and linked to particle degrees of freedom, but the quantum bound case shows that this is not always the situation.

One may see from the solutions of ((5)) that for a given E_n , there is only one $W_n(x)$ solution and so there is no further degree of freedom. One cannot adjust the interaction as in the case of maximizing entropy. In the $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ approach one also does not maximize because this expression already expresses the removal of all bias, i.e any $e_i+e_j = E_1$ has the same $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ so there is no bias. Similarly any $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$.

Thus, we suggest that even in a statistical problem, one should not always expect an entropy expression which is to be maximized.

Photon Absorption

In the case of a bound state with E_n levels, there are already specific $W_n(x)$ values. It is possible for various photons to be absorbed and emitted, and even though a photon is described by $\exp(-iEt+ikx)$, this information is not used as one does not know the exact interaction which occurs. As a result, one simply tries to remove bias by suggesting that one

maximizes the total number of states subject to an average energy constraint. One may again use the MB result $\exp(-E_n/T)$ because one partitions a total energy E over E_n possible levels. The photon interaction then disappears and one really thinks only in terms of state energy levels E_n just as one thinks only in terms of e_n values for a Maxwell-Boltzmann particle. In both cases, however, one may consider this a description of the type of interaction present. Thus, even though maximizing a Shannon's entropy expression here subject to a constraint works, it is only because this is consistent with this kind of interaction description.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that what is important in describing an interacting system, even statistically, are the interactions. In some cases, as in two body interactions or the distribution of a total energy among different states, the interactions may be described in terms of the maximization of an entropy expression (to remove bias) subject to an average energy constraint. This, however, is not a general recipe, we argue.

In the case of a quantum bound state, one has $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities describing a free particle. $\exp(ipx)$ represents ruler gradations of size \hbar/p with equal weight or maximum entropy for points within each gradation. A given p , however, does not correspond to a fixed x so one cannot use $V(x)$ as changing its energy at x . Rather, $V(x)$ must represent an average energy and so should be expressed in terms of momentum probability pieces which deliver impulse, i.e. $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. The problem is that V_k has energy units and so a description of the interactions in terms of probabilities already incorporates the average energy constraint. Thus, one need only use: $KE_{av}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ with $KE_{ave}(x) = \{\sum_p a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ or $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx + V(x)W + E_n W$. VW shows the interactions or entangled entropy of $\exp(ipx)$ s with $\exp(ikx)$ s. The fact that there is a unique W for each E_n shows that there are no further degrees of freedom to be adjusted. Thus, it seems that describing a statistical problem in terms of its interactions (using probabilities) is a more general approach than expecting there to exist an entropy expression which may be maximized subject to a constraint. The entropy expression, if it exists, really describes the kind of interactions present, we argue. It seems to be linked to a kind of unbiased distribution of a total quantity among possible single states as in the case of photon absorption/emission for a set of E_n, W_n .